

D6.4 - Gendering Scientific Publications Guidelines

WP6 - Gendering Research and Teaching

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MINDtheGEPs
gender equality in research

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Abstract

This deliverable presents a set of recommended guidelines for promoting gender sensitivity in scientific publications. The objective is to provide clear and shareable instructions on conducting gender-sensitive reviews and promoting gender-aware publications. The guidelines aim to foster a more equitable and diverse scientific community by helping to mitigate biases, drive innovation, and address societal challenges by promoting gender equity in research outputs. The deliverable outlines and discusses the conduction of a workshop on gendering scientific publications guidelines, which brought together stakeholders and resulted in recommendations for enhancing the guidelines' effectiveness and impact. The recommendations emphasize cross-functional collaboration, education and training, role models and keynote speakers, accessible communication, and inclusivity in the review process. The report concludes with the next steps, including stakeholder engagement, resource development, implementation strategies, monitoring and evaluation, and dissemination of knowledge. By prioritizing these steps, the scientific community can work towards a future of equitable and inclusive scientific publishing that reflects diverse perspectives and experiences.

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Information in this report that may influence other MINDtheGEPs tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
WP6	Guidelines of planned actions for gendering research and teaching
WP8	Scientific Dissemination Plan
All	Special Issue – how to further involve men in this GEP (tbc)
All	MINDtheGEPs Book Proposal
WP4	Empow-Lab

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1) OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The objective of this deliverable is to outline a set of recommended guidelines with the purpose of promoting gender sensitivity in scientific publications. The primary goal of this deliverable is to put forward clear and easily shareable guidelines that offer detailed instructions on conducting a gender-sensitive review and fostering gender-aware publications through calls for papers. These guidelines aim to provide actionable guidance to the actors involved in the scientific publishing process (i.e., teaching and research organizations, such as students, teachers and researchers, as well as to reviewers and editors). These guidelines will also be used for training and other actions included in the project's gender equality plans.

To achieve this, the deliverable reviews existing guidelines and draws upon previous experiences in the field and uses first-hand insights from both academics and gender equality educators working within academia. Our main focus is to advocate for the inclusion of sex/gender variables in guidelines for authors and calls for papers issued by scientific journals. **However, such sensitivity cannot only be driven by a mere acknowledgement of such variables in research projects – we emphasize the necessity to include sex/gender in a way that is driven by scientific goals and in-depth exploration of the gender-related effects.** Additionally, the deliverable aims to enhance the participation and commitment of female scientists as peer reviewers, editors, publishers, and referees in research activities.

The development of MINDtheGEP's Gendering Scientific Publications Guidelines, in conjunction with the workshop, Train the Trainers (May 2023), the experiences shared by three renowned experts, and the insights shared by Elsevier in the area of gender and science, represents a significant step towards accomplishing these objectives. Furthermore, the deliverable highlights the Royal Society of Chemistry's Joint Commitment for Action on Inclusion and Diversity in Publishing as an exemplary model for working towards inclusivity in scholarly publishing.

By attaining these objectives, deliverable 6.4 endeavors to contribute to creating a more equal, diverse, and impactful scientific community that can effectively address global challenges.

2) WHAT DOES IT MEAN TO GENDER SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS?

Gendering scientific publications involves integrating gender analysis into all stages of the research and publishing process. This ensures that research questions, methodologies, and communication of findings are inclusive, unbiased, and sensitive to gender-related factors. By considering the impact of gender, researchers can contribute to a more equal and diverse scientific community. Gendering scientific publications encompasses:

- Incorporating gender-sensitive research design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation,
- Promoting gender equality in the research community, addressing bias, discrimination, and barriers faced by researchers,
- Using gender-sensitive language and perspectives in writing and publishing to foster inclusivity and avoid reinforcing stereotypes.

By implementing gender guidelines in scientific publications, we can advance knowledge, address societal challenges effectively, and promote equal opportunities for all researchers.

2.1) Why gender equity in research matters

Gender equity in research holds immense importance for several reasons. It is widely recognized by the European Commission¹, including the European Institute for Gender Equality², and the United Nations³, as crucial for achieving sustainable development and societal advancement. By fostering a diverse and inclusive research community, we can:

Mitigate biases and discrimination: Overcoming barriers and biases allows researchers of all genders to contribute their unique perspectives and expertise, resulting in more robust and unbiased research outcomes.

Promote comprehensive understanding: Gender equity encourages the exploration of a wide range of research questions, leading to more holistic and nuanced insights into scientific phenomena.

Drive innovation and progress: Embracing gender equity harnesses the full potential of all researchers, fostering creativity and innovation. Diverse perspectives contribute to more impactful and socially relevant research outcomes.

Address societal challenges effectively: Gender equity in research ensures that the interests, needs, and experiences of all individuals are considered, allowing for the development of solutions that are inclusive and beneficial to society as a whole.

By striving for gender equity in research, we create a more equitable, diverse, and impactful scientific community that can effectively address global challenges.

3) GUIDELINES FOR GENDERING SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

In the pursuit of enhancing sex and gender equity in research, MINDtheGEPs recognizes the importance of cross-cutting themes that transcend specific guidelines. The following overarching principles form the foundation of MINDtheGEPs' approach to Gendering Scientific Publications Guidelines:

Integration of SAGER Principles:

The foundational approach of MINDtheGEPs acknowledges the relevance and value of the Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) guidelines. These guidelines provide a comprehensive framework for reporting sex and gender issues in study design, data analysis, and interpretation of findings. The acknowledgment of SAGER principles forms an integral part of the basis for MINDtheGEPs' considerations.

¹ European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2020). Gendered innovations 2: how inclusive analysis contributes to research and innovation: policy review. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2777/53572>.; European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2021). She figures 2021: gender in research and innovation: statistics and indicators. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2777/06090>.

² European Institute for Gender Equality. (2023). Evidence to action: gender equality and gender mainstreaming in the COVID 19 recovery. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2839/05678>

³ UN Development Programme (2021). Gender equality strategy 2022-2025. Available at: <https://genderequalitystrategy.undp.org/>

Disciplinary Relevance:

MINDtheGEPs recognizes the diverse nature of scientific disciplines and tailors its approach to be universally applicable while remaining adaptable to the specific nuances of various research areas. This ensures that the guidelines are not only comprehensive but also maintain relevance across a spectrum of fields.

Inclusive Language Advocacy:

Beyond existing guidelines, MINDtheGEPs places a strong emphasis on promoting inclusive language in scientific publications. The project actively fosters language that is welcoming and accessible to a diverse audience, aiming to avoid biases and stereotypes.

Practical Implementation Tools:

MINDtheGEPs emphasizes the provision of practical tools and resources to implement gendering guidelines effectively. These tools aim to facilitate seamless integration into the research and publication workflow, ensuring that the guidelines are not just theoretical but actionable in practice.

Continuous Adaptation and Improvement:

Recognizing the dynamic nature of research and societal norms, MINDtheGEPs maintains a commitment to a flexible approach. The guidelines are subject to continuous improvement to ensure their alignment with advancements in gender equity in scientific publications.

The workshop entitled “Gendering Scientific Publications – 2nd MINDtheGEPs Train the Trainers Workshop” (see Annex 1 – workshop programme) and conducted in May 2023 in Belgrade brought together trainers from MINDtheGEPs partner organizations, field experts, publishers, and project members, totalling over 40 participants⁴. Facilitated by the University of Gdansk and Elsevier, the workshop aimed to effectively incorporate gender considerations into scientific publications and co-generate guidelines that benefit the European research community.

3.1) Recommendations for Guidelines

During the workshop, each group focused on examining existing guidelines and identifying areas for improvement. They also discussed how to make the guidelines more applicable and effective in academia. The goal was to generate recommendations that would enhance the implementation and impact of gendering scientific publications guidelines. The following are the recommendations proposed by each group:

⁴ Workshop trainers and attendees came from: Serbia, University of Belgrade; Poland, Jagiellonian University and University of Gdansk; Ireland, Munster Technological University, Tralee; Italy, University of Turin, National Research Council of Italy; Spain, CTAG – Automotive Technology Centre of Galicia; Europe: Elsevier; Italy: Knowledge & Innovation.

Figure 1 - Recommendations: Students, MA and PhD Group

<p>a) Students MA and PhD Group Recommendations</p>	Provide gender-sensitivity training for MA and PhD students, focusing on understanding the significance of sex and gender.
	Ensure that the guidelines document is communicative and informative, offering definitions and examples where necessary.
	Introduce the guidelines during journal clubs or team/lab meetings to promote awareness and discussion.
	Develop video tutorials or visual representations to effectively communicate the ideas and principles of gendering scientific publications.
	Encourage gender-sensitive referencing and citation practices to promote inclusivity.
	Include a checklist reminder for authors to use inclusive language in their publications.

The **Students MA and PhD group** highlighted the significance of gender-sensitivity training for students and recommended its incorporation into MA and PhD programs. They emphasized the need for communicative and informative guidelines, introducing them through journal clubs or meetings, and utilizing visual tools. Promoting gender-sensitive referencing, citation practices, and inclusive language were also important aspects identified by the group.

Figure 2 - Recommendations: Senior Researchers & Supervisors, Academic Teachers Group

<p>b) Senior Researchers & Supervisors, Academic Teachers Group Recommendations</p>	Mandate courses for educators to learn about gendering guidelines, and conduct a university-wide survey to determine the baseline understanding of the issue.
	Tailor the delivery of guidelines to specific scientific disciplines for more effective application.
	Promote peer-to-peer support networks to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing.
	Appoint gender ambassadors who can champion gender equality initiatives within academic institutions.
	Encourage the attendance of conferences from various disciplines and promote related discussions on social media.
	Emphasize the importance of gender considerations rather than adopting a checkbox approach.
	Introduce gendering guidelines from the first year of university through module-based teachings, influencing students' perspectives from the beginning (in Instagram, social media, stickers)

The **Senior Researchers & Supervisors, Academic Teachers group** focused on empowering educators to champion gender equality initiatives. They recommended courses and surveys to enhance educators' understanding of gendering guidelines. Tailoring guidelines to specific disciplines, promoting peer support networks, and appointing gender ambassadors were also proposed. Encouraging conference participation and social media discussions, as well as introducing guidelines early in students' academic journeys, were emphasized.

Figure 3 - Recommendations: Editor and Reviewers

c) Editor and Reviewers Recommendations	Accreditation for gender reviewers
	Finding incentives for reviewers (recognizing their work)
	Instructions about key terms through videos
	Including people from research group in the research
	As editor, ask about the management of the group (focus also on gender composition)
	As editor, thinking about reviewers' diversity.
	Import the filtering of the reviewers' database (gender, geography, disability, act)
	Reviewers should have access to research team composition.

The **Editor and Reviewers group** focused on promoting diversity and inclusivity in the review and publication process. They recommended accrediting gender reviewers and recognizing their work through incentives. Providing instructions via videos, including underrepresented groups in research, and considering the acknowledgment of diverse groups as an editor were emphasized. The group also recommended implementing a filtering system in the reviewers' database and granting reviewers access to research team composition. It is worth noting that the recommendation to 'include people from research group in the research' has sparked a controversial discussion during the workshop.

Figure 4 - Recommendations: Gender Equality Educators

d) Gender equality educators Recommendations	Implement credited courses on biases with a general focus.
	Develop courses that address specific gender issues within scientific disciplines.
	Establish a podcast/blog that provides accessible information to a wide network of students.
	Create a PhD welcome package including basic gender-related information, which can be shared across different institutions.
	Invite role models, especially in STEM fields, to serve as keynote speakers.
	Incorporate gender guidelines into summer schools and other PhD student gatherings.
Launch a QR code campaign at campuses, linking to easily digestible materials presented in a visually engaging format, such as "F bombs."	

The **Gender Equality Educators group** emphasized the importance of incorporating gender considerations into educational practices. Their recommendations include implementing credited courses on biases, developing discipline-specific courses, and creating accessible platforms like podcasts/blogs. They also proposed the inclusion of gender guidelines in PhD welcome packages and promoting role models in STEM fields. Additionally, they highlighted the need for gender guidelines in summer schools and utilizing visually engaging materials through a QR code campaign. They also highlighted that sex/gender variables included in scientific projects should not only be aiming at detecting sex/gender effects that are statistically significant as this might unintentionally foster the concept that sex differences are strong in magnitude. They called for more caution when establishing gender-related research goals so that they are not only limited to mere quest for sex differences but rather are realized by aiming for gender-sensitive research design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

3.2) Guidelines for Gendering Scientific Publishing Process

Analysing these recommendations reveals key cross-functional insights that guide the development and implementation of effective strategies for promoting gender equity in scientific publishing. That is to say:

An Integrated Approach:

The recommendations emphasize the need for an integrated approach involving educators, researchers, students, editors, and reviewers. This cross-functional collaboration is crucial for effectively implementing gendering guidelines and fostering a culture of inclusivity in scientific publishing.

Education and Training:

Several recommendations highlight the importance of education and training. Accredited courses on biases, discipline-specific delivery of guidelines, and gender-sensitivity training for MA and PhD students and educators are seen as vital steps towards increasing awareness and understanding of gender issues in academia and knowledge on how to develop gender-sensitive research projects.

Role Models and Keynote Speakers:

Including role models, particularly in STEM fields, as keynote speakers is an impactful way to inspire and motivate researchers. By showcasing successful individuals who embody gender equality principles, we can foster a culture that encourages and supports gender diversity in scientific publications.

Accessible Communication:

Podcasts, blogs, video tutorials, and visually engaging materials are recommended to make gendering guidelines more accessible and engaging for a wide range of audiences. Such communication channels can effectively convey the importance of gender considerations and provide practical examples and guidance.

Inclusivity in Review Process:

The recommendations for accrediting gender reviewers, promoting reviewer diversity, and providing access to research team composition aim to enhance inclusivity and transparency in the review process. These measures can mitigate potential biases and ensure a more equitable evaluation of scientific publications.

The trajectory of MINDtheGEPs (and its implementing partners) aim to outline ongoing initiatives and emerging directions to foster gender equity in academia and scientific publishing. We define though 4 TARGETS to be taken under consideration while we introduce the **Gendering Publishing Process**:

1. Target – Early Career Stages of Academic Pursuits

- *Integration of Gender-Sensitivity Training: Guiding Future Paths:* The sustained underscores MINDtheGEPs' commitment to laying the foundation for inclusive research practices. This initiative continues to provide practical guidelines for the next generation of academics, fostering gender sensitivity from the outset of their academic journey.
- *Emphasis on Communicative Guidelines: Guiding Through Communication:* The ongoing emphasis on communicative and informative guidelines, introduced through forums like journal clubs and meetings, with visual tools, ensures that guidelines are not merely theoretical but become integral to academic communication. This focus remains a key guideline for MINDtheGEPs, shaping a culture of inclusivity.
- *Promotion of Inclusive Language Practices: Guidelines for Inclusive Scholarly Communication:* Advocacy for gender-sensitive referencing, citation practices, and

inclusive language in scholarly communication continues to be a vital guideline. MINDtheGEPs strives to institutionalize these practices, making guidelines a practical reality in academic communication.

2. Target – Faculty and Mentors

- **Empowering Educators: Guiding Educators as Change Agents:** Continuing courses and surveys for educators, empowering them to champion gender equality initiatives, exemplifies MINDtheGEPs' focus on guidelines that empower agents of change. These guidelines for educators play a pivotal role in shaping academic institutions.
- **Discipline-Specific Tailoring: Guidelines Tailored to Disciplinary Realities:** MINDtheGEPs recognizes the importance of tailoring guidelines to specific disciplines. This ongoing initiative acknowledges the diverse nature of academic fields, providing guidelines that are not only relevant but also effective.
- **Peer Support Networks: Guidelines for Collaborative Support:** The encouragement of peer support networks and the appointment of gender ambassadors align with guidelines collaboratively developed by MINDtheGEPs' implementing partners. These guidelines aim to cultivate collaborative support within academic institutions, advancing gender equity initiatives.
- **Early Integration: Guiding Early Introduction:** Advocacy for the early introduction of gendering guidelines in students' academic journeys, encouraging conference participation, and fostering discussions on social media platforms are guidelines for early integration. These guidelines have continued to shape the academic experience since its inception.

3. Target – Review and Publication Process

- **Accrediting Gender Reviewers: Guiding Recognition of Contributions:** The ongoing practice of recognizing and accrediting gender reviewers, providing incentives, is a guideline that acknowledges the invaluable contributions of reviewers. These guidelines reinforce transparency and inclusivity in the review process.
- **Instructional Videos: Guiding Reviewer Guidance:** The development of instructional videos to guide reviewers, focusing on the inclusion of underrepresented groups in research, is a forward-looking guideline. This initiative ensures that guidelines are not just words on paper but practical tools for reviewers.
- **Diversity in Reviewer Database: Guiding Diversity and Transparency:** Implementing a filtering system in the reviewers' database for enhanced diversity, along with providing access to research team composition, stands as a guideline. These guidelines aim to enhance transparency and diversity in the review process.

4. Target – Educational Practices within Academic Settings

- **Credited Courses on Biases: Guidelines for Bias Awareness:** The implementation of credited courses on biases, fostering awareness and understanding among students and educators, is a MINDtheGEPs' guideline. These guidelines contribute to addressing implicit biases within academic settings.
- **Accessible Platforms: Guiding Information Dissemination:** Creation of accessible platforms like podcasts and blogs for disseminating gender guidelines and information is a guideline

for widespread dissemination. MINDtheGEPs aims to ensure that guidelines are accessible to a wide audience.

- **Visual Engagement: Guiding Visual Appeal:** The utilization of visually engaging materials, such as a QR code campaign, is a guideline for making guidelines visually appealing and accessible. These guidelines ensure that educational materials are both informative and engaging.

With a focus on these future directions, MINDtheGEPs acknowledges the practical implications of gendering scientific publications guidelines, working towards a more equitable and inclusive future for the academic community. With seven implementing partners actively implementing gender equality plans, MINDtheGEPs aims to make these future initiatives not only theoretical but also practical and reachable across gendering university practices.

CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

Gendering Scientific Publications Guidelines provides valuable recommendations that can contribute to advancing gender equity in academia. Building upon the insights gained during this workshop and the developmental process of this deliverable, the following conclusions and next steps are drawn:

Stakeholder Engagement: It is crucial to engage and involve all relevant stakeholders, including academic institutions, publishers, funding agencies, professional societies and researchers (see figure 10). Their endorsement and active participation in implementing the recommendations are vital for effecting systemic change. Collaboration and coordination among these entities will create a strong foundation for fostering gender equity in scientific publishing.

Development of Resources: To support the implementation of the recommendations, it is necessary to develop comprehensive resources such as training modules, guidelines documents, and toolkits. These resources should be easily accessible, user-friendly, and adaptable to different scientific disciplines and educational levels. By providing practical guidance and educational materials, we can empower researchers, educators, and institutions to incorporate gender considerations effectively.

Implementation Strategies: Devise strategies to integrate the recommendations into existing academic structures (e.g., MINDtheGEPs' Empow_Lab). This may involve incorporating gendering guidelines into university curricula, establishing mandatory training programs for educators, and partnering with journals to adopt inclusive practices in the review process.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Establishing mechanisms to monitor the progress and impact of the implemented recommendations is crucial. Periodic evaluation of the initiatives will help identify areas for improvement and ensure accountability in achieving gender equity goals. By collecting and analysing data, we can measure the effectiveness of interventions and ensure accountability in achieving gender equity goals.

Dissemination and Knowledge Sharing: Promoting the dissemination of best practices, success stories, and research findings related to gendering scientific publications is essential. By fostering a culture of knowledge sharing (e.g., through conferences, workshops, and online platforms), we can create a global community committed to advancing gender equity in academia, inspire others to take action, and learn from each other's experiences.

By prioritizing these next steps, the scientific community can work towards a future where impactful scientific publications and research reflect the diverse perspectives, contributions, and experiences of all researchers. This will cultivate a more equitable and inclusive scientific landscape, where gender equality is embedded in all aspects of research and publishing.

ANNEX 1 – Train the Trainers Workshop Programme

Workshop Methodology and Structure

❖ Setting the scene

An overview of the project’s deliverables was presented, focusing on two key initiatives:

- D6.1 - Guidelines of planned actions for gendering research and teaching (submitted)
- D6.4 - Gendering scientific publications guidelines (issue at hand)

❖ Guest speakers

The workshop included a diverse range of perspectives on gender equality, featuring guest speakers who shared their insights and experiences. Elsevier provided perspectives on gender equality at the researcher and managerial level. A subsequent interview forum provided valuable viewpoints from Isabel Goldman, Leading Edge editor at Cell and Inclusion & Diversity Officer at Cell Press, Londa Schiebinger, Director of the Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering, and Environment Project at Stanford University, and Shirin Heidari, Chair of the Gender Policy Committee at the European Association of Science Editors (EASE).

❖ Hands-on session – working groups

The workshop transitioned into a hands-on session facilitated by the University of Gdansk. Participants were divided into four working groups based on different perspectives within academia:

- a) Students - MA and PhD
- b) Senior Researchers & Supervisors Academic Teachers - MA and upper levels
- c) Reviewers and Editors
- d) Gender Equality Educators (teachers, trainers, mentors, etc.)

❖ Reference material

Each participant received a set of SAGER Guidelines and SAGER Checklist, which served as a key reference point during the working groups. The spread of editorial policies for gender and/or sex-based analysis was also provided (see chapter 4 for more information).

❖ Analysis and brainstorming

The working groups analysed the SAGER guidelines and discussed what aspects needed improvement or modification. Participants brainstormed on how to make the guidelines more effective and applicable in academia. The goal was to develop seven recommendations, per working group, based on the discussions and insights generated during the session.